

Job satisfaction mediates the effect of job stress on organizational commitment

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(02), 927–935

Publication history: Received on 09 April 2023; revised on 18 May 2023; accepted on 21 May 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.2.0924>

Abstract

This research was conducted at the Secretariat of the Provincial Legislatives Council Badung Regency. The total population and sample in this study were 73 people using the saturated sample method. Collecting data using a questionnaire which is then tested for validity and reliability. The data analysis technique used is path analysis and the Sobel test. The results in this study are

- Job stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction with a correlation value of -0.555 and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$.
- Job stress has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment with a correlation value of -0.199 and a significant value of $0.004 < 0.05$.
- Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment with a correlation value of 0.515 and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$.
- Job satisfaction can mediate the effect of Job Stress on organizational commitment with the calculation results obtained $t_{count} (3.097) > t_{table} (1.994)$.

Suggestions in this study are that the division of tasks and responsibilities must be based on the abilities that employees have so that they do not cause employee Job Stress.

Keywords: Job Stress; Job satisfaction; Organizational Commitment; Employee

1. Introduction

Human resources (HR) are one of the important assets of an organization or company that manages other resources owned by the organization effectively and efficiently to achieve organizational goals (Simamora, 2016). One of the efforts made by the organization in managing Human Resources is by building employee organizational commitment. According to Kingkin et al. (2010), organizational commitment is the focus of the company, because the commitment of members of the organization is important for an organization in creating the survival of an organization regardless of its organizational form. Therefore, commitment between individuals and organizations must be conditioned in a balanced state and can be directed at achieving organizational goals (Sinambela, 2019: 317).

Employee commitment is one of the keys that also determines the success or failure of an organization in achieving its goals. Employees who are committed to the organization usually show a working attitude that is attentive to their duties, they are very responsible for carrying out their duties and are very loyal to the agency where they work. With a commitment someone will express determination to do something. In commitment there is confidence, a binder that will generate energy to do the best. In real terms, commitment has an impact on the work performance of human resources and in the end it also greatly influences the performance of an organization or company (Damrus, 2018).

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According to Wibowo (2019: 198) what can affect organizational commitment is Job Stress where Job Stress has direct consequences for the organization such as decreased work productivity which can result in relationships between co-workers, employee absenteeism and absenteeism from work and changes in attitudes in a negative direction. However, if stress can be managed properly, it can increase motivation to work and have a positive view of the career path so that existing Job Stress can be turned into maximum work results (Ekawarna, 2018). In addition, job satisfaction can also affect organizational commitment where someone who feels satisfied in his work will have motivation, commitment to the organization and high work participation so that they will continue to improve their performance. But employee job dissatisfaction can be identified from low employee productivity, high absenteeism at work and low commitment to the organization (Sinambela, 2019).

Wibowo (2019: 188) defines Job Stress as a psychological response to demands that have certain stakes for human resources and which burden or exceed the capacity of these human resources. According to Tewal et al, (2017) stress in the work environment cannot be avoided, but Job Stress can be reduced or managed so that it does not interfere with work. Job Stress if managed properly can be a driving force and increase work intensity, employees will feel challenged and need to exert all their abilities to excel and thus be able to complete tasks properly. However, if the employee's Job Stress level is high and it is not immediately resolved it can have an impact on behavior that is not expected by the organization, such as low job satisfaction and decreased organizational commitment of employees (Putri, 2015). From this opinion it was found that job stress can affect job satisfaction and will impact on organizational commitment.

Job stress experienced by employees greatly influences their satisfaction with work. According to Sinambela (2019: 317) the higher the Job Stress experienced by employees, the more dissatisfied they will be in their work. The higher the stress felt or experienced by the employee, the higher the stress level that the employee will have. This stress level will then affect employee commitment where the higher the stress level an employee has, the lower their commitment to the organization. Meanwhile, according to Norhayati (2019) Job Stress experienced by employees if it is managed properly, including workload, will not cause stress so that commitment to the organization will be higher.

Job satisfaction will occur if workers feel that the value they want is fulfilled. Something that is valuable or has value is anything that is consciously or unconsciously sought or obtained by that person. According to Wibowo (2019: 142) job satisfaction has a positive and strong influence on organizational commitment. People who get a higher level of job satisfaction tend to feel a higher level of commitment, namely affective commitment (commitment that arises because of emotional closeness to the organization) and normative commitment (commitment related to workers' feelings about the need to remain in the organization).

The secretariat of the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council as one of the organizations in government that functions to provide services to the Provincial Legislatives Council requires good commitment from employees because it influences the success of the institution. The Secretariat of the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council is tasked with carrying out secretarial administration, financial administration and supporting the implementation of the duties and functions of the council. Therefore, government agencies need to ensure that their employees are superior human resources and are able to help institutions achieve their goals. One of the keys to organizational success in the current era of globalization is the extent to which employees within the organization are synergistically able to contribute positively, both in planning and in the process of implementing duties and responsibilities as employees in the organization to achieve organizational goals. Commitment must be owned by employees who work in government agencies.

Organizational commitment of Non-Civil Servant Employees can be seen through the absentee level of Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat which indicates that employee organizational commitment is still not optimal. The absentee level for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat is an indicator of the level of commitment to the organization so that it can be concluded that the average absentee level for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat from January to December 2020 with a percentage of 3.01. An absence of 0 to 2 percent is considered good, 3 percent to 10 percent is considered high, and above 10 percent is considered unreasonable (Flippo, 2012). Absence of employees without reason is a situation that is detrimental to the institution.

The results of observations and interviews that have been conducted with Non-Civil Servant Employees show that the Job Stress experienced by Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat is an indicator of Job Stress that looks like physiological symptoms, namely employees who are easily emotional, sensitive, unable to relax, and have headaches. Workload and time pressure cause stress on employees. The increasing workload faced by employees can increase stress. Employees are faced with various problems such as high workload and more and more

erratic duration of working time which must be completed in a limited time due to changes in schedules and plans decided by Provincial Legislatives Council leaders who follow developments in the existing situation and conditions.

Likewise the results of interviews that have been conducted with Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat that the job satisfaction they feel is that the work assigned to employees is too much, the salary discrepancy earned with the workload carried out by employees, there is no promotion carried out by superiors, work performed by employees sometimes exceeds the time of the specified working hours but no additional income has been earned by employees.

The purposes of this study are (1) to analyze the effect of Job Stress on job satisfaction for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat, (2) to analyze the effect of Job Stress on organizational commitment to Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat, (3) to analyze the effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment to Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat, (4) to analyze the role of job satisfaction in mediating the effect of Job Stress on organizational commitment to Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Organizational Commitment

According to Muthuveloo and Rose (2015) stated organizational commitment as employee acceptance, involvement, and dedication to achieving organizational goals and employee willingness to accept organizational values and participate in all organizational activities towards organizational improvement. According to Colquitt et al. (2017) organizational commitment is the desire of some workers to remain members of the organization. Organizational commitment influences whether an employee remains a member of the organization or leaves the organization to pursue other jobs. Likewise, according to Kaswan (2012) states that organizational commitment is a measure of employee willingness to stay with a company in the future.

2.2. Job Stress

Stress can mean a feeling of tension, anxiety or worry experienced by employees. Such feelings are a form of the experience of stress, a complex response to feelings of threat that can have positive or negative outcomes. Stress is defined as a psychological response to demands that have a certain effect on the person and which burden or exceed the capacity of the person (Wibowo, 2019: 188). Meanwhile, according to Ekawarna (2018: 142) Job Stress is people's responses when work demands and pressure are not in accordance with their knowledge and ability to overcome them. This Job Stress can cause unstable emotions, feelings of unrest, likes to be alone, unable to think positively and experience other psychological disorders.

2.3. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work, how he feels about his work and what he thinks about his work concerning emotional states, both pleasant and unpleasant for employees to view their work. According to Mcshane and Von Glinow (2018) view job satisfaction as a person's evaluation of his work and work context which includes an assessment of job characteristics, work environment and perceived emotional experience at work. Meanwhile, according to Sinambela (2019: 302) job satisfaction can be defined as the level of positive affection of a worker towards work and work situations. Job satisfaction is always related to the attitude of workers towards their work. This attitude takes place in the cognitive and behavioral aspects.

The hypothesis in this study namely H1: Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat, H2: Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat, H3: job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment to non-Civil Servant employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat, H4: job satisfaction mediates the effect of Job Stress on organizational commitment at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat.

3. Material and method

Based on theoretical studies, the conceptual framework in this study is the Secretariat of the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council as one of the regional apparatus organizations of Badung Regency which certainly requires maximum organizational commitment from its employees to achieve organizational goals. One of the factors that must be considered to achieve high organizational commitment is the need to manage Job Stress which can have an impact on employee job satisfaction. Employees who feel overwhelmed by work demands beyond their capacities and abilities can experience Job Stress (Wibowo, 2019). Job stress can also affect organizational commitment. If an employee's Job Stress level is high, it may have an impact on unexpected behavior towards the organization, such as a decrease in employee organizational commitment (Putri, 2015). If the Job Stress of employees in the organization is managed properly, it will affect employee satisfaction. Someone who is satisfied with his job has high motivation, organizational commitment and work participation so that he can continuously improve his performance (Wibowo, 2019). Based on the explanation of the relationship between variables, the conceptual framework of this study is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

The location of this research was conducted at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat which is located at Jl. Raya Sempidi, Mengwi District, Badung Regency. The population and sample in this study were all Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Secretariat of the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council, totaling 73 people. Determination of the sample under study was carried out by nonprobability sampling method using saturated sampling technique. Data collection methods used observation, interviews and questionnaires, then the answers to the statements on the questionnaire were tested for validity and reliability so that they were suitable for use as research instruments. The data analysis method used is path analysis and the Sobel test.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that there were 51 people or 69.9% of respondents who were male, dominated by respondents aged 20 to 30 years who were 45 people or 61.6%, respondents with high school education were 41 people or 56.2%, which means that more dominant employees of the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat are high school graduates and the highest number of respondents are respondents who have worked for 2-5 years as many as 56 people or 76.7%.

Table 2 can be explained that all variables have a correlation coefficient or Pearson correlation value above 0.30, thus all of these instruments are valid, so they are worthy of being used as research instruments and the Cronbach Alpha coefficient value is above 0.60, so that all of these instruments can be said reliable.

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

No	Characteristic	Classification	Total (person)	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Man	51	69.9
		Woman	22	30.1
		Total	73	100.0
2	Age	20-30 yrs	45	61.6
		31-40 yrs	20	27.4
		41-50 yrs	8	11.0
		Total	73	100.0
3	Education Background	High School	41	56.2
		Diploma	1	1.4
		Bachelor's degree	31	42.5
		Total	73	100.0
4	Year of Services	< 2 years	3	4.1
		2-5 years	56	76.7
		> 5 years	14	19.2
		Total	73	100.0

Table 2 Research Instrument Testing

No	Research variable	Statement Items	Validity		Reliability	
			Correlation coefficient	Information	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
1	Job Stress(X)	X.1 – X13	>0.30	Valid	>0.60	Reliable
2	Job satisfaction(Z)	Z.1-Z.14				
3	Organizational commitment(Y)	Y1-Y10				

Primary Data, 2022

Table 3 can be explained that the respondent's perception of the Job Stress variable at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat is in the medium category with an average value of 2.93. Respondents' perceptions of the job satisfaction variable at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat are in the high category with an average value of 4.03 and respondents' perceptions about the organizational commitment variable at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat are in the high category with an average value of 4.05.

Table 3 Description of Respondents

No	Variable	Statement Items	Average Score	Category
1	Job Stress(X)	X.1 – X13	2.93	Fair
2	Job satisfaction(Z)	Z.1-Z.14	4.03	High
3	organizational commitment(Y)	Y1-Y10	4.05	High

Primary Data, 2022

Table 4 Coefficients of Substructure 1 (Model 1)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	77.576	3,374		22.994	0.000
	Job Stress	-0.555	0.088	-0.601	-6.338	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Primary Data, 2022

Table 5 Coefficients of Substructure 2 (Model 2)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	19.014	5.885		3,231	0.002
	Job Stress	-0.199	0.066	-0.263	-3,022	0.004
	Job satisfaction	0.515	0.071	0.628	7.226	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment

Primary Data, 2022

Table 6 Direct Effect, Indirect Effect, and Total Effect

Variable		Direct Effect	Indirect Effect Through Job Satisfaction	Total Effect
Job Stress	Organizational Commitment	- 0.199	-0.555 x 0.515 = 0.285	0.484
Job Stress	Job satisfaction	- 0.555		-0.555
Job satisfaction	Organizational Commitment	0.515		0.515

Primary Data, 2022

Total determination coefficient results:

$$R^2m = 1 - (1-R1^2) (1- R2^2)$$

$$R^2m = 1 - (1 - 0.361) (1 - 0.662)$$

$$R^2m = 1 - (0.639)(0.378)$$

$$R^2m = 1 - 0.241$$

$$R^2m = 0.759$$

That is, the diversity of data that can be explained by the model is 0.759 percent or in other words the information contained in the data is 75.9 percent can be explained by the model, while the remaining 24.1 percent is explained by other variables (not contained in the model) and error.

4.1. Job Stress on Job Satisfaction

Based on the calculation results, it is obtained that the research significance level for the variable Job Stress on job satisfaction with a correlation value of -0.555 and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, in other words the first hypothesis, Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on Job satisfaction for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat is acceptable. This means that the increasing Job Stress of Provincial Legislatives Council employees outside the Civil Servant will reduce the level of employee job satisfaction, conversely if the Job Stress is low it will increase the job satisfaction of Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat. The results of this study support the research of Pratama and Sriathi (2015), Ariana and Riana (2016) and Dewi and Netra (2015) which show the same results, namely Job Stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. The higher the Job Stress experienced by a person, the lower his job satisfaction.

4.2. Job Stress on Organizational Commitment

Based on the calculation results, it is obtained that the research significance level for the Job Stress variable has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment with a correlation value of -0.199 and a significant value of $0.004 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted, in other words the second hypothesis, Job Stress has an effect negative and significant impact on organizational commitment to Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat is acceptable. This means that the increasing Job Stress of Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat will reduce their organizational commitment, whereas if Job Stress is low it will increase the organizational commitment of Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat. The results of this study support research conducted by Wibowo et al (2015), Damrus et al (2018) and Putri and Martono (2015) also show that Job Stress has a negative impact on organizational commitment. The higher the job stress, the lower the organizational commitment.

4.3. Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment

Based on the calculation results, the research significance level is obtained for the variable job satisfaction on organizational commitment with a correlation value of 0.515 and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so that H_0 is rejected and H_3 is accepted, in other words the third hypothesis, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on commitment Organizational support for Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat is acceptable. This means that increasing employee satisfaction for non-Civil Servant employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat will also increase organizational commitment, whereas if job satisfaction is low, it will reduce employee organizational commitment. The results of this study support research conducted by Taurisa and Ratnawati (2012), Puspitawati and Riana (2014) and Akbar et al (2016) that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. The higher the employee's job satisfaction, the higher the employee's commitment to the organization.

4.4. Job Satisfaction Mediates Effect of Job Stress on Organizational Commitment

Based on the calculation results obtained $t_{count} (3.097) > t_{table} (1.994)$ thus job satisfaction can mediate the effect of Job Stress on organizational commitment. This means that the mediation or indirect effect of job satisfaction on Job Stress has a significant effect on organizational commitment to Non-Civil Servant Employees at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat. The results of this study support research conducted by Legowo et al (2019), Wirawan and Dewi (2020) and Permatasari and Rahyuda (2020), which show that job satisfaction mediates the effect of Job Stress on organizational commitment. That is, the emergence of Job Stress experienced by employees does not directly affect organizational commitment but through job satisfaction. Therefore, the type of mediation in this study can be explained by the fact that the direct effect of job stress on organizational commitment is -0.199, the direct effect of job stress on job satisfaction is -0.555 and the effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment is 0.515. Compared to the degree of indirect effect of job satisfaction, which is 0.285, the magnitude of the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect

5. Conclusion

Based on the data obtained from the results of the analysis it can be concluded that:

- The variable of work stress has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction with a correlation value of -0.555 and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.
- For the variable work stress has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment with a correlation value of -0.199 and a significant value of $0.004 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted.

- The variable of job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment with a correlation value of 0.515 and a significant value of 0.000 < 0.05, so H0 is rejected and H3 is accepted.
- The calculation results obtained $t_{count} (3.097) > t_{table} (1.994)$ thus job satisfaction can mediate the effect of work stress on organizational commitment.

Suggestions in this study are

- Assigning tasks and responsibilities to suit the abilities of employees.
- Giving confidence to employees that employees have the ability to complete tasks properly.
- Employment opportunities and development of career paths for employees who work at the Badung Regency Provincial Legislatives Council Secretariat so that employees have no desire to leave the organization.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The researchers acknowledge and appreciate all the mothers who participated in this study

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research.

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